

EUROPEAN POLICY BRIEF

Why inclusion needs to be at the forefront of citizen science

INTRODUCTION - The importance of inclusion in citizen science

Citizen science involves the active participation of members of the public in voluntarily contributing to research, including by asking research questions, collecting and/or analysing data, and using the results. The data generated by citizen science groups have become an increasingly important source for researchers, as well as for institutions and agencies pursuing the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. Citizen science aims to bring the broader public into research, with benefits ranging from increased efficiency compared with traditional data collection methods, to the growth of science capital¹. However, it is often the same people who participate in citizen science initiatives - those who are highly educated, and who can afford the time and effort to engage in participatory activities². Most citizen science initiatives struggle to engage underrepresented or vulnerable groups.

This policy brief:

- Sets out the key benefits of more inclusive citizen science initiatives.
- Presents an overview of the key barriers to implementing inclusive citizen science, whilst maintaining a focus on the practical implementation of inclusive citizen science.
- Makes recommendations for practitioners, local decision makers and funders about what can be done to further enhance inclusion in citizen science.

Throughout, we draw on examples from the IMPETUS accelerator programme, which supports new and existing citizen science initiatives to address the issues around inclusion and diversity in citizen science more broadly.

What is inclusion in citizen science?

The United Nations (UN) defines social inclusion as the process of improving the terms of participation in society, particularly for people who are disadvantaged, through enhancing opportunities, access to resources, voice and respect for rights. Inclusivity in citizen science refers to the equitable involvement of diverse societal groups in research. This means ensuring that people of different ages, genders, sexual orientations, disabilities, ethnicities, socioeconomic statuses, legal statuses and educational backgrounds have the opportunity to participate³.

1. Varga, D., Doran, C., Ortega, B. and Segú Odriozola, M. (2023) 'How can Inclusive Citizen Science Transform the Sustainable Development Agenda? Recommendations for a Wider and More Meaningful Inclusion in the Design of Citizen Science Initiatives', *Citizen Science: Theory and Practice*, 8(1), p. 29. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5334/cstp.572>
2. Vasiliades, MA, Hadjichambis, AC, Paraskeva-Hadjichambi, D, Adamou, A and Georgiou, Y. 2021. A Systematic Literature Review on the Participation Aspects of Environmental and Nature-Based Citizen Science Initiatives. *Sustainability*, 13(13): 1–27. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13137457>
3. Varga, D., Doran, C., Ortega, B. and Segú Odriozola, M. (2023) 'How can Inclusive Citizen Science Transform the Sustainable Development Agenda? Recommendations for a Wider and More Meaningful Inclusion in the Design of Citizen Science Initiatives', *Citizen Science: Theory and Practice*, 8(1), p. 29. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5334/cstp.572>,

Inclusivity in citizen science initiatives can manifest in several ways:

- **Engaging underrepresented groups:** efforts are made to actively involve communities and individuals who are traditionally excluded from scientific endeavours. This includes marginalised communities and those from lower socio-economic backgrounds.
- **Co-design and participatory approaches:** inclusivity is also achieved through co-design, where community members are not just participants but co-creators of the research process. This participatory approach ensures that the research addresses the concerns and needs of diverse groups.
- **Methodological inclusivity:** the tools, methods, and outputs of citizen science initiatives (such as data collection methods, technology, creative outputs, and research impacts) are designed to be accessible and beneficial to a broad audience.

The benefits of inclusive citizen science

Citizen science approaches are not only more efficient compared with traditional data collection methods, but can also benefit all participants through building participants' confidence, providing opportunities to learn new skills and deepening participants' understanding of research. Inclusive citizen science has cascading impacts:

- **Inclusive citizen science can generate more complete, richer datasets.** For example, the Heat Watchers in Action initiative in Barcelona⁴, Spain, sought to shed light on the unequal effects of climate change, with a particular focus on heat and thermal discomfort in urban low-income households with children. The project used citizen science to understand and disseminate the urban impacts of climate change, working with over 100 children, 33 families, 11 teachers and 145 other stakeholders in low-income neighbourhoods to co-create solutions to foster resilience. Five new datasets were published at the end of the project, generating a rich source of data on urban indoor heat stress that includes a child-oriented perspective.
- **Inclusive citizen science can tackle specific knowledge gaps around the experience of underrepresented groups that may have previously been excluded.** In the case of the London Borough of Islington's Accessibility Audits⁵, the project sought to integrate the lived experience of 12 residents with reduced mobility, generating essential information on obstacles found on streets and pavements, taking a pan-disability perspective. The initiative co-designed the accessibility audits with the participant group and embedded residents with reduced mobility's lived experiences into urban planning in Islington. This ensured future audits are more effective and genuinely take into consideration residents' needs.
- **Inclusive citizen science can generate data with and for groups affected by an issue, making them more visible in research.** For example, Obstetric Coevolution⁶ sought to address the lack of data and resources on the mental health of postpartum women, particularly the need to rethink the birth experience, in Barcelona, Spain. The initiative developed a new tool - the birth diary (carnet de Salut)-specifically tailored for mothers and perinatal professionals to collect data on all the processes needed to foster continued assistance throughout the birthing process. The data generated with participants was used to help predict and reduce the risk of post-partum depression or post-traumatic stress disorder.
- **Citizen science initiatives can be transformative for those participating in them, building understanding and cohesion between groups with different experiences.** The benefits to participants include psychological and cognitive skill development through hands-on activities, social skill development through collaborative activities, improved physical and mental health, higher well-being and life satisfaction, and increased tolerance and understanding towards other individuals⁷. The new knowledge and skills, social capital and empowerment can lead to longer lasting behaviour changes. For example, the Acting4DHH⁸ initiative was initiated by Web2Learn⁹

4. <https://impetus4cs.eu/heat-watchers-in-action/>

5. <https://impetus4cs.eu/london-borough-of-islington-accessibility-audit/>

6. <https://impetus4cs.eu/obstetric-coevolution-obcoe/>

7. Varga, D., Doran, C., Ortega, B. and Segú Odriozola, M. (2023) 'How can Inclusive Citizen Science Transform the Sustainable Development Agenda? Recommendations for a Wider and More Meaningful Inclusion in the Design of Citizen Science Initiatives', *Citizen Science: Theory and Practice*, 8(1), p. 29. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5334/cstp.572>

8. <https://impetus4cs.eu/acting4dhh/>

9. <https://web2learn.eu/>

and the Deaf Association of Northern Greece (EKVE) to understand and promote interactions between deaf and hearing individuals, and to address accessibility issues in public urban spaces in Thessaloniki, Greece. Deaf and Hard of Hearing (DHH) citizens are often excluded from participatory initiatives that affect their quality of life and wellbeing in urban settings. 30 DHH participants produced 25 videos of their experiences of DHH-Hearing interactions, mapping challenges and opportunities in DHH-hearing collaborations and communication in everyday settings. A collaboration of 20 DHH and Hearing participants also mapped 10 public spaces through a public urban monitoring app (IMC). The collaboration between the DHH participants and Hearing participants, facilitated throughout the initiative activities, created community bonding and solidarity between the two groups, with the outcome of helping to overcome social biases and barriers.

- **Inclusive citizen science fosters meaning, social purpose and connection.** This can lead to increased environmental stewardship and climate resilience. For example, Map4Rec¹⁰ engaged Ukrainian refugee children in the active exploration and mapping of informal places for sports and recreation in 6 cities in the Twente region of the Netherlands. Through indoor workshops and neighbourhood walks, the initiative co-designed location-based games to map the perceptions and use of urban green spaces. Participants used the Epicollect app, documenting their perceptions, and suggesting improvements resulting in a map with 152 locations¹¹. Their tailored methodology engaged children in missions related to environmental mapping, biodiversity monitoring, sports and health, which fostered connection to urban recreational spaces, promoting wellbeing and environmental stewardship.
- **Inclusive citizen science also provides opportunities for different stakeholders to interact, going beyond the usual networks of collaborators and participants.** Collaborations between researchers, public sector organisations and the public in citizen science activities can lead to the improved management of local and context-specific issues, more effective participation of the public, in particular underrepresented groups, in local decision-making processes¹². For example, Oeiras Experimenta¹³ set out to study and identify climate resilient crops through the restoration of a secular farm and the implementation of a multi-disciplinary research hub in Oeiras, Portugal. The initiative is a collaboration between researchers and the municipality, with a representative of the municipality being part of the core project team. The initiative involved the public in activities on the farm around crop sowing, harvesting and field maintenance to raise awareness about climate resilient crops. The initiative also collaborated with two social inclusion organisations and the local educational centre for institutionalised youth, integrating underrepresented groups in the research hub, and giving them greater visibility in the research activities.
- **Inclusive citizen science can support more inclusive policy and decisions.** Dear Green Place¹⁴ - an initiative focussed on the mental health of young people in urban green spaces in Edinburgh, Scotland - engaged 55 young people, in collecting data on urban green spaces using the Our Outdoors app, as well as generating evidence on how local shared outdoor spaces affect health and well being. The initiative worked with a smaller number of young people (8-10 people) to meet the needs of those with neurodiversity and lower levels of digital literacy, who needed more support using the app. The initiative also connected the young participants with local policy makers at Edinburgh Council to have their say on their local green space developments. The initiative continues to work with the Council as they develop other urban green space initiatives to ensure that young people's voices are heard in every stage of that process.

10. <https://impetus4cs.eu/map4rec-second-edition/>

11. <https://five.epicollect.net/project/map4rec/data>

12. Sauermann, H., Vohland, K., Antoniou, V. et al. (2020) Citizen science and sustainability transitions. *Research Policy*, Volume 49, Issue 5, 103978. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2020.103978>

13. <https://impetus4cs.eu/oeiras-experimenta-climate-smart-crops-for-sustainable-food-production/>

14. <https://impetus4cs.eu/dear-green-place-promoting-wellbeing-in-young-people-with-our-outdoors/>

- **Inclusive citizen science is time and resource intensive, more so than a typical citizen science approach. Successful engagement strategies require time and flexibility to meet communities where they are.** Too often, citizen science initiatives underestimate what is needed to meaningfully engage underrepresented communities. This includes raising and managing differing expectations, and managing competing timeframes, as well as managing the follow through at the end of a project, and after a project has formally ended. This goes beyond taking time to implement good citizen science. For example, the first iteration of the Acting4DHH project tried to engage the Deaf and Hard of Hearing (DHH) community in undertaking biodiversity monitoring using the iNaturalist platform¹⁵. However, there were low levels of engagement in the project activities and few members of the target group attended events and activities. The project activities were not tailored to the interests of the target group. In the second iteration of the project, during the IMPETUS accelerator, the project team took a much more flexible approach, using citizen social science to better adapt to the requirements of the DHH community, adjusting the project activities to accommodate the needs, interests, and motivations of participants. This involved reducing the number of proposed activities, slowing down the overall cadence of the project, and spending more time and effort to ensure that all those involved in the project were aligned on objectives and terminology. In particular, since written outputs are not a direct translation of sign language, more time was needed to develop appropriate materials for the project.
- **Inclusive citizen science involves navigating both doing science (Citizen Science) and meaningfully engaging participants in activities (Citizen Science).** Consideration needs to be given to when decisions are made about the direction of the project, and at what point in the project cycle, and who gets to make the decisions. Working with schools can be effective for developing in-depth co-design approaches. However, there is a risk of compromising on the scientific outcomes in favour of engaging target participants in activities. For example, the Museum of Food Waste¹⁶ engaged 6 schools across 2 municipalities in northern Portugal to collect data on the quantities of food waste generated in school canteens. The initiative co-designed the data collection approach with students, canteen staff and school teachers to facilitate both meaningfully engaging target groups and also creating replicable protocols for data collection on food waste. The protocols enabled quantitative data collection on 3 types of food waste, and qualitative data collection on the behavioural aspects of food waste prevention. The toolkit for data collection has been adapted to a wider public of children aged 10-15 years old to ensure it is accessible and replicable in other schools and municipalities across Portugal.
- **Citizen science relies on people contributing in their free time, for free, which isn't possible for many people, particularly groups who are typically underrepresented.** Initiatives need to think about remuneration or other incentives to support engagement. For example, the Luna project¹⁷ was developed in Ljubljana, Slovenia to address the lack of scientific data on phenomenology throughout the menstrual cycle. Luna engaged 87 citizen scientists with menstrual cycles to collect real-time data, reporting daily reflections. Whilst the initiative didn't offer remuneration, it did offer participants access to their own data on their own menstrual cycles, and the opportunity to investigate personal research questions in a supported environment.
- **There is a risk of reifying differences by only working with 'vulnerable groups'.** If citizen science initiatives claim to engage "everyone", it is often only the most privileged and dominant groups that engage. It is crucial to purposefully involve people who are not the (social) majority in citizen science initiatives. The Austrian Citizen Science platform Österreich Forscht¹⁸ has developed transparent criteria for projects wishing to be listed on the platform to maintain and further improve the quality of the projects presented on the platform. The check list of quality criteria enable citizen science initiatives to consider which groups they are excluding in their work. Instead of asking how inclusive they are, they ask who is left out and this stimulates a reflexive process in which the limits of a project can be better understood and tackled. This has been crucial for project leaders to acknowledge the limitations of participation in citizen science initiatives.

15. <https://inaturalist.org/>

16. <https://impetus4cs.eu/the-museum-of-food-waste>

17. <https://impetus4cs.eu/luna-the-experiential-landscape-of-a-menstrual-cycle/>

18. <https://citizen-science.at>

Citizen science has significant potential to contribute to stronger social inclusion and social sustainability but is currently failing to live up to this. Programmes like the IMPETUS accelerator and associated projects are starting to make headway in addressing this issue. IMPETUS has funded over 120 citizen science initiatives, supporting them to be more inclusive both through the funding selection criteria, specific training on engagement and communication strategies, tailored mentoring and also through the tracking of diversity statistics in the target groups and project teams. However, more work is needed if citizen science is to fulfil its potential. This section sets out some clear recommendations for both citizen science practitioners, as well as local decision makers and funders to achieve more inclusive citizen science in Europe.

Recommendations for practitioners and citizen science project leaders:

- Collect demographic data on project participants, whilst being mindful of the data minimisation principle, and make the anonymised data publicly available to enhance the wider understanding of different participant profiles,
- Consider the context specific requirements of inclusion taking into account local social realities. While it is not possible to make every citizen science project accessible to everybody, project organisers should aim for an inclusive design by taking into account the local context of the issue they are trying to address. Working with intermediary organisations can help with this.
- Design initiatives in a way that is open to underrepresented groups, even though the specific target audience depends on the scope of the project and is highly context specific. If this mindset is adopted and shared among all stakeholders from the outset, every step of an initiative can be designed inclusively or corrected along the way.

Recommendation for local decision makers:

- Collaborate with local citizen science initiatives to make use of the data they have generated to inform local priorities and decision making.
- Take a citizen science approach to tackle different knowledge gaps and gaps in evidence for policy making, such as accessible mobility in urban planning, by having a specific social inclusion dimension.
- Any targeted focus on engaging underrepresented groups needs to factor in time and flexibility to build up relationships and adapt engagement strategies to the target groups, especially if they are vulnerable.

Recommendations for funders:

- Develop funding calls tailored to underrepresented groups and that necessitate inclusion within the application criteria - see the IMPETUS programme for a successful example. This could include micro- grants with simplified application procedures and reduced reporting obligations (potentially through a cascading grants mechanism).
- Funding programmes should also factor in additional time allowances for participants to build connections with key stakeholders and develop good working relationships with aligned expectations before the engagement in research activities. Additional time allowances may also be necessary for relationship management and fading out after the research phase.

PROJECT NAME	IMPETUS
AUTHOR	Alexandra Albert, IMPETUS Policy Lead, Centre for Collective Intelligence Design, Nesta, London, UK alexandra.albert@nesta.org.uk Contributions from Dr. Antonella Passani, T6 Ecosystems and Dr Gefion Thuermer, Kings College London.
CONSORTIUM	Ars Electronica, Linz, Austria European Science Engagement Association, Vienna, Austria King's College London, London, United Kingdom Nesta, London, United Kingdom Science for Change, Hospitalet De Llobregat, Spain T6 Ecosystems srl, Roma, Italy Zabala Innovation Consulting, S.A., Navarra, Spain
FUNDING SCHEME	IMPETUS is funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 101058677. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.
DURATION	July 2022 – June 2026 (48 Months)
BUDGET	5,000,000 Euros, Contributed by the European Commission and the UK Research and Innovation
WEBSITE	https://impetus4cs.eu/
FOR MORE INFORMATION	This policy brief is part of the IMPETUS citizen science innovation programme's work on enhancing policy for citizen science, working with policy makers, funders and research institutions to better understand and support the citizen science ecosystem.
Acknowledgments	We would like to thank our collaborators from the European Citizen Science project - the ZSI-Centre for Social Innovation GmbH - and particularly Dr. Barbara Kieslinger and Stefanie Schuerz - for all their input and review of this policy brief.